

SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE AND SOCIOCULTURAL ASPECT OF LANGUAGE.

Xamrayeva Nilufar Xamidullayevna

Dotsent TSTU named after Islom Karimov

Abstract. In order to maintain interpersonal relationships, it is necessary to understand culturally deep-rooted ways of politeness used within each society. It is one of the main elements of sociolinguistic competence and therefore the following chapter focuses on this subject.

Key words. Sociolinguistic competence, strategic competence, target language, cultures and linguistic and non-linguistic politeness.

XUSHMUOMALALIK VA UNING SOTSIOLINGVISTIK KOMPETENSIYA BILAN ALOQASI.

Annotatsiya. Millatlararo bog'liqlikni o'rganish, shunga o'xshash mavzular doirasida izlanishlar olib boorish, ular oorasidagi munosabatlarni saqlab qolish uchun har bir jamiyatda qo'llaniladigan xushmuomalalikning madaniy jihatdan chuqur ildiz otgan usullarini tushunish kerak. Bu sotsialingvistik kompetentsiyaning asosiy elementlaridan biridir va shuning uchun keyingi bobda ushbu mavzuga e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Ijtimoiy lingvistik kompetentsiya, strategik kompetentsiya, maqsadli til, madaniyatlar va lingvistik va nolingvistik xushmuomalalik.

Hymes encapsulates this competence as the patterns of sociolinguistic behaviour of the target language which represents the rules of speaking. Discussing the theory of sociolinguistic dimensions, Hymes analyses the concept of verbal repertoire suggested by Gumperz (1964); the concept of linguistic routines and the domains of

language behaviour elaborated by Fishman (1966, p. 424-39). These three theories participate on clarifying the major aspects of the competence: the capacities of persons; the organisation of verbal means for socially defined purposes and the sensitivity of rules to situations.

Another point of view can be found in English Language teaching (2010, vol.3 p. 146). Muniandy perceives sociolinguistic competence as sociocultural rules of language and discourse in which case it is important to understand the social context of the language consisting of the rules of participants, the shared information and the functions of the interaction. In this sense, one of the elements of the competence Muniandy regards is the sensitivity to dialect or variety of English in respect to the fact that Malaysian English variety has been classified as three 'sociolects' ranging from 'high' social to 'low' social dialect. And likewise, sensitivity to registers is mentioned to belong to capabilities influencing sociolinguistic understanding of any language.

Wolfson (2014, p. 62-63) approves of the idea of different patterns of interaction existing within diverse speech communities whose members share understanding of adjusting the speech conduct according the particular situations. Besides considering what is appropriate to say and when including conversational topics and forms of address there are also speech acts (e.g. greetings, compliments, apologies, invitations and complaints) that are to be used, interpreted and a suitable reaction needs to be chosen. Otherwise it can lead to communication failure to such extent that mutual trust can be damaged and further development of relationship almost impossible with the participants facing unintended insult, injustice or harm in spite of the speaker's intentions. Finally, Hymes' (1972) term of communicative interference can be likened to a literal translation of the rules of speaking of one speech community to another.

The claim of significant influence of distinctive features of society and its culture on its members in communication enlightens the role and importance of sociocultural competence.(Hasil et. all, 2006 p.182). All five levels of language (phonetics, morphology, syntax, semantics and pragmatics) are being modulated fundamentally by

these aspects and for this reason they require assiduous attention in order to reach meaningful and effective communication in order to avoid communication misunderstanding.

As a conclusion of the above-mentioned ideas, it is the matter of fact that culture plays important role in the process of developing relations between the members of groups with different cultural identity. And therefore, it is crucial to comprehend the notion of culture in its whole.

Relationship between sociolinguistic and pragmatic competence: Companion Volume with New Descriptors to Common European Framework of Reference for Languages newly issued by Council of Europe (CVND to CEFR, 2018 p. 132) reflects the above-mentioned models in the chapter 1 and in respect to the term of communicative competences distinguishes: linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competence. The pragmatic competence is closely related to the sociolinguistic competence therefore the following chapter provides an overview of the pragmatic aspect.

Pragmatic competence: Pragmatic competence is distinguished from linguistic competences by the definition of its scope of activity and that is "the actual language use in (co-) construction of text". It is divided into three main subsections: discourse, functional and design competence. Discourse competence in particular deals with organisation, structure and arrangement of messages. Functional competence answers the question how is a message used for communicative function. The last one, within the frame of interactional and transactional schemata, focuses on sequencing of messages. One component of this competence is Flexibility which is in effect "use of one's repertoire and selection of appropriate selection of sociolinguistic choices". There is an association between the comprehension of interactional and transactional schemata and sociolinguistic competence and for this reason it comes under "Sociolinguistic appropriateness".(CVND for CEFR 2018, p. 140-141)

Pragmatic competence relates to sociolinguistic competence in terms of the

meaning of utterance in the context. It deals with understanding of the rules of language use and consists of discourse, functional and design competence. The way ideas are structured and organised it is the matter of discourse competence. Their communicative functions are summarised in functional competence and design competence represents interactional patterns and processes. Pragmatic competence is closely pertained to social dimension of a language. It can be likened to computer hardware with its software in a form of sociolinguistic competence.

Leech's definition of pragmatics that describes how utterances have meanings in situations brings us back to the key concept - the meaning. It encompasses this field. (Leech, 1983, p. X) Likewise, the fact that speaker's meaning' in context may differ from 'the sentence/dictionary meaning' is relevant to pragmatics and it elicits the importance of precise formulation denoted as 'Propositional Precision'.

Moreover, there are two points mentioned as summarisation of theoretical approaches of pragmatics related to context and the use of speech acts . The first is the need to raise awareness of learners to specific features of speech acts. Particularly, tendency to be used in a form of 'semantico-syntactic' pattern and on

habitual basis. Speech acts are implemented in a sequence of steps which prompts their application or decision whether to use them or not answering questions: when, where, how and with whom. The second point is importance of knowledge of 'interactive or sociocultural principles underlying language usage' that refer to politeness theory. (Moron et al., 2009, p. XV)

References:

- 1) Applegate, R. B. (1975). The language teacher and the rules of speaking. TESOL Quarterly. 9, 271-281.
- 2) Archer, C.M. (1986). Culture bump and beyond. In J.M. Valdes, Culture bound: bridging the cultural gap in language teaching (pp. 170-178). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- 3) Blum-Kulka, S. (1983). Interpreting and performing speech acts in a second language- a cross cultural study of Hebrew and English. In N. Wolfson & E. Judd (Eds.), *Sociolinguistics and language acquisition* (pp. 36-55). Rowley: Newbury House.
- 4) Blum-Kulka, S., House, J., & Kasper, G., (Eds.). (1989). *Cross-cultural pragmatics: requests and apologies*. Norwood: Ablex.
- 5) Clancy, P. (1990). Acquiring communicative style in Japanese. In Scarcella, R., Anderson, E., and Krashen, S. (Eds.), *Developing communicative competence in a second language* (pp. 27- 40). New York: Newbury House.
- 6) Cohen, A.D., & Olshtain, E. (1983). Apology: a speech act set. In N. Wolfson & E. Judd (Eds.), *Sociolinguistics and language acquisition* (pp. 18-35. Rowley: Newbury House Publishers.
- 7) Cohen, A.D. & Olshtain, E. (1991) Teaching speech act behavior to nonnative speakers. In M.Celce-Murcia (Ed.), *Teaching English as a second or foreign language* (2nd ed.) (pp. 154- 165). Boston: Heinle & Heinle.
- 8) Nigmatovna, Y. N. (2021). WIDE USE OF ROLE GAMES IN MODERN TEACHING METHODS. INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRACTICE. *SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL*, 2, 115-122.
- 9) Nigmatovna, Y. N. (2020). Principles for effective teaching and learning foreign language. *International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education*. Yusupova, N. N. (2023). PEDAGOGIK TA'LIM KLASTERI MUHITIDA ARALASH TA'LIMNI QO'LLASH TEXNOLOGIYASI. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(19), 224-230.
- 10) Xamrayeva, N. (2023). MEANING ASPECTS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH EDUCATIONAL PROVERBS. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(5), 770-773.
- 11) Xamrayeva, N., & Olimova, M. (2023). SOTSIOLINGVISTIKA VA

DIALEKTOLOGIYA. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(6), 149-154.

12) Yusupova, N. N. (2022). Intensive Learning of English in the Pedagogical Educational Environment on the Basis of Media Technologies. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 5666-5674.